

85 wet seasons relating yield to agronomic traits of rainfed lowland breeding lines. Water depth was maintained at 25 to 50 cm from 3 wk after transplanting to maturity. We tested 75 entries in 1983, 73 in 1984, and 64 in 1985. They included check cultivars and advanced breeding lines, with entry changes each year.

Grain yields were low in 1983 and 1984 (0.6-3.0 t/ha), but were as high as 4.9 t/ha in 1985. They did not correlate well with agronomic traits. In 1984, a

subset of 25 entries was grown under shallow (5 cm) water depth. Grain yield for medium deepwater and shallow conditions correlated positively ($r = 0.66$), indicating that yield potential at both water depths was related. Tillering did not correlate with yield nor differ between depths. Plant heights averaged 138 cm over all entries under medium deep conditions, compared to 131 cm under shallow conditions. Average lodging score by *Standard evaluation*

system for rice (SES) was 5.5 in medium deepwater and 2.6 in shallow water.

Twenty-one breeding lines were included in all years' trials. Correlations between years were low. Several breeding lines performed better than check cultivars (see table).

In selecting lines for medium deep conditions, it is important to conduct yield trials over several years and select for intermediate plant height and lodging resistance. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Spikelet sterility in three rice cultivars

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Spikelet deformity was observed in three rice cultivars at ARS farm in rabi 1983 (Oct-Mar), late rabi 1984-85 (Feb-Jun), and rabi 1985-86. Sterility ranged from 4 to 29%. When panicles were opened at booting, the androecium and gynoecium were already aborted and the lemma

and palea in florets were twisted. Most florets were aborted (see figure).

IR20 in rabi 1983, and Rasi and IR50 in late rabi 1984-85 and 1985-86 were

observed for sterility in the field. IR20 recorded 4.3%; Rasi, 28.8%; and IR50, 15.2% sterility (see table). The suspected cause of the high sterility in IR50 is high temperature from panicle initiation to flowering. The higher temperatures might have affected meiosis, resulting in sterility. □

Spikelet sterility in 3 rice cultivars and weather parameters during panicle initiation to flowering. ARS, Nellore, India, 1983-86.

Cultivar	Hills affected (%)	Panicles affected (%)	Total spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Weather parameter ^a		
					Maximum temp (°C)	Minimum temp (°C)	Relative humidity (%)
IR20	100	100	134.5	4.3	28.9	21.1	85.1
IR50	100	90	76.5	28.8	38.1	26.9	71.8
Rasi	100	100	66.4	15.2	37.0	26.0	70.3

^a Rainfall was nil during the trials.

Characteristics of sterile spikelets under high temperature at panicle initiation.

Hybrid rice responses to high temperature at flowering

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We studied hybrid rice responses to high temperature at flowering in the phytotron and under natural climatic conditions in southeastern Sichuan, China. Panicles of hybrids Shan You 2 and Ai You 2 that emerged 50-60% at the same growth stage were observed. Before temperature treatments, spikelets that had undergone anthesis were cut. After treatment, unbloomed spikelets were cut.

In the phytotron, spikelets treated with a constant day temperature of 27, 29, 31, 33, 35, 37, and 39 °C for 6 consecutive hours from 0800 to 1400 h had sterility percentages of 10.0, 11.5, 7.7, 9.2, 15.8, 26.4, and 74.3%, respectively. Thus the percentage of sterility increased as temperature increased beyond 35 °C, a correlation significant at 1% level.

Sustaining the high temperature progressively increased sterility. Sterility was 15.5, 26.6, and 28.8% when the spikelets were treated at 35 °C for 2, 4, and 6 h, respectively.

Spikelet sterility induced by natural climatic high temperature was observed during flowering in fields in southeastern Sichuan, China. Results (see table)

Percentage of spikelet sterility induced by high temperature under natural climatic condition in southeastern Sichuan, China.

Method	Daily mean temperature (°C)	Daily maximum temperature (°C)	Sterility (%)	Spikelets or panicles observed (no.)
Spikelet treatment	27.9 ± 1.02	32.4 ± 1.75	7.24 ± 1.64	11,984
	31.27 ± 1.12	36.35 ± 1.11	10.85 ± 2.05	7,719
Panicle treatment	27.2 ± 1.10	31.35 ± 2.39	14.87 ± 2.84	200
	30.87 ± 0.06	35.27 ± 0.25	21.93 ± 1.36	150

indicate that daily mean temperatures 30 °C or lower and daily maximum temperatures 35 °C or lower significantly affected spikelet sterility.

To determine the stages most sensitive to high temperature, we treated 2,636

spikelets at meiosis, 778 at pollen grain development stage, and 1,320 at flowering, using 35 °C for 4 h in the phytotron. This induced 4.1% sterility at meiosis, 5.3% at pollen grain development, and 15.8% at flowering.

The index of heat tolerance (% fertility at high temperature/ % sterility at normal temperature) for hybrid rices Shan You 2 and Ai You 2 were determined at 33, 35, and 37 °C in the phytotron. Heat tolerance for Shan You 2 was 1.05, 0.78, and 0.14; that for Ai You 2 was 0.84, 0.42, and 0.09, respectively. Thus Shan You 2 tolerated high temperature better than did Ai You 2.

Adopting high temperature-tolerant varieties and adjusting flowering times are strategies to avoid high temperature sterility. □

Adverse soils tolerance

Modified screening method for salt tolerance

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We developed a practical method to screen rice varieties for salt tolerance, based on IRRI's screening techniques. Some modifications have been made:

1. Rice seedlings are planted in soil fertilized with NPK instead of raised in solution culture, simplifying the screening of more varieties at lower cost.
2. Screening is fixed at the 3-leaf stage to eliminate the unfavorable effects caused by 2-wk-old seedlings grown in different seasons.

3. At 4 wk after transplanting (WT) the plants are scored by both the percentage of dead leaves and the salt injury symptoms (visual), and IRRI's standard of score 2 and score 1 are merged into score 1.

We have tested 1,580 rice varieties, including some of IRRI's resistant and susceptible checks such as Nona Bokra, Pokkali, Kalarata, and Damodar, by this modified method. Results are similar to those with IRRI's technique. The procedure is as follows:

- Germinate rice seeds in demineralized water.
- Plant the pregerminated seeds in soil fertilized with NPK.
- Irrigate up to 1 cm depth until seedlings reach the 3-leaf stage.
- Pull the seedlings without injuring the roots, wash the roots in water, and select

four good uniform seedlings from each variety.

- Plant them in a tray (41 × 27 × 13 cm) filled with 7 kg clay loam soil, and add 5.6 liters of 0.5% common salt solution to the soil. The ECE of the soil saturation extract should be 8-10 dS/m. Plant tolerant and susceptible checks.
- Add demineralized water whenever necessary.
- Score at 4 WT, using percentage of dead leaves and leaf injury symptoms (see table). □

Results of screening rice plants for tolerance for salinity, using a modified method. CNRRI, China, 1988.

Dead leaves ^a (%)	Reaction to salinity	Score	Tolerance degree
0-35	Normal growth, absence of salinity symptoms	1	Highly tolerant
36-50	Restricted growth and tillering, a few rolling leaves	3	Tolerant
51-70	Very restricted growth and tillering, most leaves rolling	5	Moderately tolerant
71-90	Growth ceases, most leaves and some plants dead	7	Moderately susceptible
91-100	Most plants dead or nearly dead	9	Susceptible

^aPercentage dead leaves = $\frac{\text{no. of dead leaves/plant}}{\text{no. of leaves/plant}} \times 100$.

Rice yield responses in a saline soil in Sri Lanka

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In the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka, 10% of riceland is coastal saline. Pokkali is one of the few adaptable varieties, particularly where soil conductivity goes up to 7-8 dS/m. However, Pokkali is not widely grown because it has low yields and is susceptible to lodging and diseases.

This study compared two promising salt-tolerant cultivars with Pokkali at 2 spacings in 1985-86 wet season in a farmer's field with salinity up to about 7 dS/m.

Two-week-old seedlings of Bw 272-8, Bw 297-2, and Pokkali from a dry bed